

Proposed design for national-county WESM framework

v1.2

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1. Introduction

1.1. Aim of this document

This report is submitted to show how the tasks under Output 1 have been met, namely -

- 1a. Develop a conceptual understanding of the National-County framework. This framework will be used to scope model boundary, organize data flows and map the functionality for running the multi-scale model.'
- 1b. Translate experience of using similar workflow / approach in UK multi-scale modelling to national-county framework
- 1c. Document the workflow. This will involve creating a record of the steps involved in developing and running the model.

The main part of the report describes the proposed conceptual framework for a national-county whole energy system model that is to further support the integration of energy planning efforts at county and national governance scales (Output 1a). It describes the concept for multi-scale model set up itself, its development, as well as its implementation in the form of a minimum viable product. The document is now being used to guide development of the framework. An earlier version of the report was presented to Kenyan county and national stakeholders in June 2024, to facilitate feedback on the process. The feedback is summarised in Annex 2 (A2), and cross-referenced in the main report.

The report also provides information on the UK approach to multi-scale modelling (Output 1b), which is being used to underpin the modelling approach described here for Kenya (see Box 2 in particular). Finally, the workflow for developing and running the model (Output 1c) is outlined in Section 3.

1.2. Context

The Energy Act 2019 of Kenya states that 'Each County Government shall develop and submit a county energy plan [CEP] to the Cabinet Secretary in respect of its energy requirements' (5.3). The draft Energy (Integrated National Energy Plan) Regulations 2023 has put forward a process for the responsibilities of different committees and the integration of energy and county plans into the Integrated National Energy Plan (INEP). This legislation highlights both the importance of the county energy planning process but also the need for integration into the national INEP framework.

A recent review of the county energy planning process stated that six counties had so far completed their CEPs, with a further 15 counties currently developing their plans (Ngaira et al. 2023; Leonard et al. 2023) – see Annexes 1. Since this review, another county has completed the process so a total of seven counties have finalised their CEPs. Of those completed and available for review (Nakuru, Kitui, Narok), different approaches have been taken to energy planning and different modelling tools employed, including OnSSET and LEAP (Ngaira et al. 2023). The majority of CEPs are being

supported via the Sustainable Energy Technical Assistance (SETA) programme, in collaboration with the European Union.

The approach to county-level planning is crucial to ensuring that local priorities around energy demand are planned for, and the necessary investment in energy supply are made. However, as noted in the above EED Advisory report, there are currently some challenges to the development of CEPs. These include lack of sufficient capacity to undertake planning, provision of external support that does not engender sustainable capacity, and lack of data for use in plans and guidance to develop CEPs.

Furthermore, once developed, there is then the need to integrate CEPs into the INEP framework. This is also a challenge due to differences in -

- *Timescales for CEP completion.* Plans are being developed on different timescales, which makes it challenging to aggregate all CEPs to form a complete national picture.
- *Approaches used for CEP development.* Different approaches are being taken, leading to variation in outputs. For example, Mwendwa et al. 2023 compared CEPs for Nakuru, Kitui, and Narok, noting differences in methodology and content.
- *Data availability.* As noted, this can be a constraining factor on the ability to develop CEPs, with variation in availability across counties.
- *Scenario analysis.* Each county developed its own scenarios, based on different assumptions which makes it difficult to aggregate the outputs.

The challenges of data availability and relative progress on CEP development were both confirmed based on stakeholder interaction undertaken as part of this work (see Annex 2). It is in this context that UK PACT Phase 2 is providing support to enable the aggregation of county level insights into a national modelling framework. To do this, we propose the development of a county-national model framework to help support integration and alignment of planning across these governance levels (as described in the next section).

Design of a county-national model

A national OSeMOSYS energy systems model (Kenya WESM) has been developed by CCG in collaboration with partners in Kenya and is currently being used and developed further (Box 1). It is a single node model but captures the whole energy system – and can therefore help support the INEP. However, the INEP process also needs to take account of the CEPs being developed for 47 counties in Kenya. The overarching proposal for this work is therefore to develop a county-disaggregated version of the national OSeMOSYS model within a flexible multi-scale modelling framework.

This structure can facilitate the incorporation of county specific information, including from CEPs where they are either completed or in progress. This project will build the model structure and help populate it with relevant data. Where CEP outputs are not available, county level data from national providers and downscaled national datasets can be used – but then updated in the future as and when CEP-specific data become available.

It is important to stress that this framework is not intended to replace modelling undertaken to inform CEPs – but rather as a supporting modelling framework that helps ensure that county planning priorities can be represented at the national level.

Box 1. Kenyan Whole Energy System Model (Kenya WESM)

Kenya WESM is built using the modelling platform OSeMOSYS (or Open-Source energy MOdelling SYStem). OSeMOSYS is an open source, technology rich modelling framework to allow for the building of energy system representation, to undertake scenario modelling of the medium (2030s) to long term (2050) time horizon. The model uses an optimisation-based approach that builds out future systems based on projected energy service demands, with the aim to minimise the costs of doing so. It also recognises the existing system infrastructure when determining new investment, and specific conditions related to resources, technology deployment, and specific policies that will impact how the system evolves in the future. Key insights from this model include types of technologies, and levels of investment required to meet current and future energy demand. Other metrics such as level of energy imports, and sectoral emissions are also key outputs.

The Kenyan whole system model captures all the main energy using sectors of the economy, including resource (upstream), power and hydrogen production [energy supply sectors], and industry, commercial, households, transport and agriculture [energy demand sectors]. Figure 1 provides an illustration of the model structure – and how the system ‘fits’ together.

Figure 1. Simplified WESM reference energy system

The primary strength of Kenya WESM is as follows -

- Understanding the implications of a national strategy on all sectors. For example, a strategy focused on greenhouse gas emission reductions such as an NDC can be assessed, to estimate investment needs of reducing emissions across the economy.
- Assessing the interactions between sectors. For example, the Kenyan WESM has been used to assess the implications of an increase in e-cooking on the power sector.
- Assessing resource distribution. The modelling can also help determine how different energy resources are used across the energy system.
- Understanding the role of different technologies. Due to the technology explicit nature of the model, all assumptions related to individual and classes of technology can be assessed e.g. cost, efficiency, deployment rate etc.

The Kenyan WESM [model](#) and associated [documentation](#) are available online. Note that there is also a power sector-only OSeMOSYS model for Kenya, which is described in detail in Kihara et al. 2024. The Kenyan WESM has the same power system representation as the power sector-only version.

This basic conceptual approach – a whole energy system model with county resolution – is outlined in the following sections in more detail, focused on model boundaries, data needs, and design considerations. Table 1 provides an overview of the key aspects of the conceptual framework.

Table 1. Key aspects of the conceptual framework

Framework elements	Key design aspects	Description
Model boundaries	Overall boundaries	Spatial and temporal resolution of national scale model
	County representation	Representation of specific sectors at the county level (within national representation)
Model data	Data requirements	Given model boundaries, the data requirements to enable the model design
	Data sourcing	Development of a hierarchy of data sources, and outline of possible sources of information
Model design	Workflow	Tangible steps to developing the proposed model design
	Principles	Principles underpinning the model development process

1.3. Model boundaries

We first consider the model boundary for this county-disaggregated national model. By model boundary we mean how we simplify and represent the system that we want to analyse. This includes the geography (spatial resolution), time period (temporal resolution), sectors, and actors.

To help further guide our consideration on model boundary, we first need to identify the planning objectives and priorities from the CEPs and ensure that we develop a model structure that allows for these to be incorporated. The CEPs are required to include the following technical aspects (based on Mwendwa et al. 2023) -

- **Resource assessment**, to include bioenergy and renewables assessments that enable counties to consider local resources to meet their energy needs. Key dimensions for this assessment should include availability and economic potential, adequacy, sustainability, ease of access and cost of use.
- **Energy access**. This dimension is key so that counties can plan how to increase access based on understanding of current access and necessary interventions to increase it. Information should be included on energy access initiatives and policies, access for lighting and for cooking (heating), and energy access trends for different sectors (households, community services, productive use e.g. enterprise).
- **Energy efficiency**. To ensure energy is used as efficiently as possible, this part of the plan should help identify the energy efficiency gaps, potential solutions, costs and benefits of the solutions, as well as the potential barriers and constraints in the implementation of the solutions. Sectors covered should include households (including cooking and lighting), commercial and institutional buildings, industries and the transport sector (vehicles used with and transiting, proportion of people using non-motorised transport, and motorbikes registered).
- **Bioenergy** assessment is key, in view of the reliance on bioenergy across many counties. This should therefore include 1) baseline supply of bioenergy (including bioenergy crops, agricultural, supply

cost, demand across power generation, building sector, manufacturing sector, transport sector, households and institutions) and challenges affecting the sector.

- **Electricity.** Key to ensuring access to supply and providing electricity in an affordable way. Aspects to include in this part of the plan include current and future demand and supply, key stakeholders, key challenges, and proposed interventions.

Given the requirements of CEPs, a key consideration is how to incorporate the different CEP elements into a county-resolved WESM (or CORE-WESM). Starting with the national model, the following elements of the model boundary have been considered -

- **Geography:** Kenya, disaggregated into 47 counties. As noted earlier, lack of data availability today should not preclude inclusion of a given county. Default data assumptions can be used in the first version of the model (see section 2.2) and updated as improved information becomes available.
- **Time period:** The proposed temporal resolution remains the same as for Kenya WESM, running to 2050 in annual time steps, with each year represented by 48 timeslices, obtained combining two day types, four seasons and six hour periods per day.
- **Sector and actors:** Given the focus of CEPs on specific planning aspects, our initial proposal (subject to stakeholder discussion and data availability constraints) is to ensure that the county regions of the model can represent those aspects, whilst other aspects are represented at the national level. This is important to ensure that the county-disaggregated version provides the same overall coverage as Kenya WESM. The two scale representation (county and national) should help enable this.

As shown in Figure 2, the focus of the county representation is on resources, decentralised bioenergy and electricity supply, and energy use as it relates to households, commercial, small-scale industry and agriculture. In other words, sectors most relevant to the CEP process. While transport may be a required feature of CEPs, evidence on current practice suggests that it is very difficult to characterise at the county level due to lack of data.

Figure 2. Sector representation in county-resolved WESM by spatial scale

Further review of county energy plans and elicited stakeholder views have been used to confirm the above sector split, in addition to general support for the approach (Annex 2). There were questions raised as to why associated functions around waste management and transport were not included. There was also a question as to why decentralised generation was being included, as often this was not an area of devolved oversight; however, this model is also being developed to represent aspects of the energy system that make more sense to be represented at the subnational scale – hence its inclusion.

The model framework and workflow will also be structured to allow for flexibility in disaggregating sectors as the model is further developed (see section 3). Whilst transport is captured in CEP reporting requirements under ‘energy efficiency’, we consider that the available data, based on our understanding of current plans, would make it very difficult to model this at the county level; hence our recommendation to retain this sector at the national level.

In Table 2, we have outlined some of the key considerations for each of the sector that are recommended for county level representation. Data considerations are presented in the next section. Of all of the sectors listed below, the most challenging, given data availability, are industry, commercial and institutions.

Table 2. Considerations for county representation in WESM

County sector	Design considerations
Renewable resources	Bioenergy and renewable resource potential (by type) Woodfuel and charcoal shares Bioenergy costs
Power (decentralised)	Decentralised technology options (The county regions in the model will be able to secure electricity supply from the centralised grid, modelled at the national level)
Agriculture	Energy demand for agriculture, from electricity, bioenergy and oil Note that we will use 'generic' technologies to model energy consumption / flows, as opposed to specific technologies e.g. water pumps, agricultural machinery etc.
Households	Energy demand for households, including cooking fuels and electricity Representation of energy using technologies (to also capture energy efficiency potential)
Small scale industry, commercial and institutions	Energy demand for these sectors (mainly buildings), with a focus on electricity demand but also including other energy commodities

Further, the design considerations identified above will be refined to develop model boundaries for county energy system demand projections. Such a framework will enable the representation of the identified county data into the Model for the Analysis of Energy Demand (MAED) allowing for flexibility of the captured sectors and energy end uses in the future.

1.4. Model data

The data requirements for the model (and associated repository) are being addressed under other tasks of this UK PACT project but are nonetheless crucial to consider in terms of the conceptual framework developed in this report. In particular, it is important to consider data needs and availability when considering the model boundary (as described above in Section 2.1) and in developing the overarching workflow (see Section 3).

To implement the disaggregation of national model to county level requires county level data for each of the sectors (listed in Table 2). However, we are aware that there are significant differences in the availability of data across counties, which often reflects the rate of progress across county CEPs.

We have therefore proposed that data is sourced for the model based on a hierarchy of data sources. In order of priority, the different sources include -

1. Existing data from county plans and from county administrations
2. County level datasets provided by national data providers e.g. population data from KNBS
3. National datasets downscaled to county level based on population or income data from KNBS

Source 1 is highest priority for use, whilst source 3 is lowest priority, but will act as the default option where other data are not available. This default option (3) is important to ensure the model provides a complete representation, but which can be updated based on locally sourced data becoming available. From a workflow perspective, to get the model set-up, many of the datasets may rely on downscaled data initially (Figure 3). This is to establish a *minimum viable product* (MVP) and thus to derive an initial set of input data as placeholder that can be used to operationalize the model, with the intention to refine these data in the future. It is hoped that as the project develops and engagement with counties increases, there will be a stronger push to use higher priority source 1 data.

Note that this hierarchy is not in of itself making any judgement on data quality. This will need to be considered on a case-by-case basis, based on an understanding of where the data have been sourced from, be that primary or secondary sources. It is also the case that some CEPs will have used source 2 or 3 data themselves, as opposed to collecting primary data via surveys or other means.

This hierarchy approach was presented to stakeholders at the June 2024 workshop and supported in general. There was definitely support for the use of data type 1 where this could be achieved but a recognition that other data types (2 & 3) would be needed given different levels of CEP progress and data availability across counties. It was also highlighted that even where CEPs had been progressed, data were not always in a format that could necessarily be used or transferred. Other counties, such as Turkana, are leading in this regard, with their own data depository.

Figure 3. Hierarchy of data provision to county-resolved WESM

To develop an understanding of how county level data can feed into the model, we have started to collaborate more closely with a selection of counties who have made strong progress on their CEP development and are interested in the overall approach proposed in this study, namely Turkana, Kilifi, Nakuru, Makueni and Meru. This will help provide additional insights on how to enhance the data workflow from CEPs to this national framework and refine the design of the model. Some of these counties like Meru have completed their CEPs or are in the final stage of completion like Kilifi and are thus likely to be able to provide the data we need for the modelling process. The counties selection aims to cover both rural and urban areas, to provide for a good representation of different county geographies in Kenya. To facilitate engagement, a template Excel workbook has been set up and shared with the counties so relevant data can be collected. Work on data quality under output 4 (on the data repository) will feed into the approach to identify data sources across the three tiers. For example, where county level primary data collection quality is deemed low, downscaling may provide a “better” estimate for some data needs.

With the view that county level data (where available and of good quality) will feed into the model framework, Table 3 focuses on data sources 2 & 3 that will enable the MVP.

Table 3. Proposed sources of data for source 2 (county-resolved national datasets) and 3 (national-downscaled) data sources

County sector	Data needs	Data sources
Renewable resources	Bioenergy and renewable resource potential Bioenergy costs	Global Forest Watch, Ministry of Agriculture, Global Wind Atlas, Global Solar Atlas, MSR dataset from IRENA
Power (decentralised)	Technology data Current deployment of decentralised generation	KPLC/KNBS/EPRA
Agriculture	Agricultural energy demand by fuel type – current & projected	County agricultural Department Energy balance from the IEA
Households	Household energy demand by energy service (cooking, electrical appliances etc.) - current & projected Current deployment of cooking appliances	Population, appliance ownership, lighting source, cooking type from KNBS (county-resolved datasets): - Kenya Integrated Household Budget Survey (2015-2016) - Kenya Continuous Household Survey (2019 update) - Kenya Demographic and Health Survey 2022 Energy balance from the IEA
Small scale industry, commercial and institutions	Industry, commercial and institutional energy demand by energy service	Health facilities ¹ : Ministry of Health Education facilities: Ministry of Education KNBS, Economic Survey

¹ Colleagues at Berkeley have been doing work on health facilities and decentralised power sources, this could be an opportunity to integrate their research where it benefits the modelling.

For those sectors retained at a national level resolution (as shown in Figure 2), it will be important that they only consider parts of the energy system that are not covered by the county-resolved sectors. This is a key issue for two sectors that, in the current national model, include elements that we propose to split between county and national resolutions -

- Power sector. The proposal is that decentralised options are represented at a county level. The national level sector therefore needs to only represent centralised generation and grid infrastructure.
- Industry. Small-scale industry demand is important for understanding county level energy needs (as per CEPs), and therefore is proposed for representation at the county level. The national level sector therefore needs to only represent larger scale industry; however, there remains an open question as to how small- and large-scale are differentiated – and the data available to come up with this split.

The data collection from the county level and from national providers will also feed into the data repository that is being implemented under Output 4. The data repository will allow an easy download of data in a csv format along with metadata describing its content, as well as an upload of some outputs generated by the modelling framework or data collected that could be beneficial for counties. Where possible automatic data checks will ensure data integrity such as correct data types and number of columns in a tabular dataset. Data quality and provenance could be monitored manually and indicated through tags or metadata. Ideally, all data should be publicly available but if the data provider doesn't grant permission, the option to select who can access the data will be possible. Task 4 will assess how to provide this functionality from technical and governance perspectives so that processes can be sustainable and fit for purpose.

Engagement with county stakeholders will be key to understand what data they would be interested in and what data they could provide to the data repository. Strong collaboration links between the two teams will ensure that the data that will be collected for the OSeMOSYS modelling will be uploaded in the data repository and that data uploaded in the data repository from other sources will be brought to the attention of the OSeMOSYS modellers.

1.5. Model design principles

There are number of considerations on the details of the framework and model implementation that are important in the context of planning the overall design of the model, as well as the overarching conceptual framework. These include framework functionality and accessibility, as well as model data calibration. Some of these design principles are based on experiences from a similar but UK focused project. Box 2 highlights some aspects from this UK modelling effort and how it informs the approach taken here.

Box 2. Insights from multi-scale approach implemented for the UK

A research project currently concluding at University College London has been developing a similar multi-scale approach as envisaged for this project yet with a different focus and in the context of the UK. The project aims to support multi-level governance in the UK by facilitating scenario analyses that bridge local and national level using a multi-scale energy system model. The rest of this box provides a short overview of model design principles for the UK project and how these relate to or inform the proposed approach under the UK PACT project.

Modelling framework & functionality. The UK model is implemented using a simple but flexible multi-scale modelling framework built around the core functionality of OSeMOSYS. The framework allows for flexible definition and operation of multi-scale models. Different sectors can be defined at different scales and geographic entities can be aggregated or run separately (see Figure 4 for exemplary visualizations). The functionality of this modelling framework will be adapted and used for this project.

Figure 4. Exemplary visualization of the framework functionality showing a run of single local authority run (left) and of England as whole where all English local authorities are aggregated (right).

The UK model is currently focused on the building sector, for which it covers the whole of Great Britain with a spatial resolution of local authorities (which are local government areas that are smaller than counties). It also includes supply sectors, including a power sector, that are defined at the national level.

Usability. The framework and model are Python-based. The workflow is implemented in a reproducible, adaptable, and transparent way using a workflow management package. The setup will be published alongside documentation under an open license but is relatively complex with a rather steep learning curve to operate. A web-based dashboard is currently being developed with local stakeholders to allow users to explore and compare scenarios across scales in a very accessible way (see Figure 5). This experience informs the approach for this project which intends to implement a more accessible model setup that allows for an easier uptake of the model as outline in Section 3.

Figure 5. Screenshot of the alpha version of the dashboard being developed for the UK model.

Calibration. The model relies on high-resolution, national datasets and is calibrated based on national statistics. It does not currently include local authority supplied data sets.

Functionality. It is important that the county-resolved WESM provide the necessary functionality to be of value to county and national planners involved in supporting INEP. Features of functionality include -

- Representation of local conditions and planning insights from CEPs at the national level
- Flexibility to design the spatial structure to both represent sectors at national and county resolution
- Ability to run the model at different levels of aggregation e.g. as 47 county model ‘solutions’ aggregated to the national level or as a single model solution based on the aggregation of county level data.

Usability. It is an objective of this project that the model is built in partnership with national and county stakeholders – and will continue to be developed and used after the project. To ensure that this outcome is achieved, it is important that the model is accessible and can be readily applied to energy policy questions. The UK approach used a relatively complex workflow based on Python. Consideration needs to be given to ensuring, whilst providing the necessary functionality, that the model can be used and developed post-project.

We also need to develop a strategy to determine who is the user base and how to support capacity building effectively. This will be an important consideration early in the project – but an initial

suggestion would be the CCG Kenya Special Interest Group (SIG) on energy planning with the involvement of key county stakeholders.

This was an issue raised multiple times at the June 2024 workshop in Sagana, Kenya (see Annex 2). There is a need for resources to enable county stakeholders to be involved in the above energy planning SIG, which is crucial to ensure the voices of a range of counties are heard. The UK PACT team, alongside CCG, will continue to explore ways that enable such representation, and capacity building within the county planning community on this national-county level framework.

Calibration. The UK approach ensured that sub-national regions summed to national statistics. This is an obvious approach to take when disaggregating national statistics but becomes harder if local datasets are being used in the model. Our default approach is to calibrate at the national level – based on the data in the national model.

Finally, it is important to state that this development process follows the principles established for supporting strategic energy planning by many different organisations (Roundtable Initiative on Strategic Energy Planning, 2021), which promote five key principles on -

- National ownership. A country-led energy planning processes that work in partnership with key stakeholders.
- Coherence and inclusivity. Coherent with key national objectives, a planning process that is evidence-based, integrated and inclusive.
- Capacity. Activities built into the process that strengthen the capability of national institutions to take the lead on energy planning.
- Robustness. Models used that have strong technical and economic foundations, are fit-for-purpose, are able to support flexible and adaptive approaches, and can be easily updated.
- Transparency and accessibility. Promote open access to and review of planning inputs and encourage the accessibility of planning outputs to stakeholders.

Technical implementation of the model

This section provides technical detail and workflow for the implementation of the multi-scale model. The implementation is shaped by the requirements discussed in the preceding sections, including flexibility in defining and running the model, use of various sources of input data, and its usability. In particular, the setup of the model aims to strike a balance between facilitating the complex operation of a multi-scale model and a simple model workflow that allows for relatively easy uptake and usage of the model beyond the project period. Figure 6 provides an overview over the model setup and workflow.

Figure 6. Overview over the technical model setup and workflow

The overarching core elements will be implemented as follows -

Model data set:

The core of the model setup are the required datasets for the CORE-WESM model. This includes both data for sectors modelled at the national level and data for county-level sectors for each of the 47 counties. The data set is to be organised as a set of spreadsheet files, in which the data for different sectors or government levels can be flexibly arranged as long as a certain format for the model data tables is followed. A ‘multi-scale syntax’ will be used to allow for a more user-friendly definition of values, e.g., setting a single value for where the same value is to be used for all counties. The data set will also include data defining the multi-scale structure of the model.

Data input pathways:

Data for the model data set is provided via four different routes. First, model data for national-level sectors is to be directly adopted from the Kenya WESM. This will be implemented in the form of a script that allows automatic scraping of data from the most recent Kenya WESM version. Second, county-level data can be derived from the downscaling of Kenya WESM data (data source 3, as per section 2.2). The exact implementation of this is subject to further consideration under Task 2 of the UK PACT project.

Third, county-level (and national) data from other sources can be included manually from relevant datasets (data source 2). For large datasets or datasets that are regularly updated an automatic approach using a script will be considered. Fourth, data coming from county data sheets – to be

developed under Task 2 – can be fed into the dataset (data source 1). This will again be based on an automatic process using a script. To allow for easier uptake, the intention is for this script to be running on the cloud so it can be easily used via a web browser and does not require installation of software locally.

Model runs:

Running the model will require three steps. First, a script is used to generate an OSeMOSYS data file from the model input data set. Second, the OSeMOSYS data file, together with a model file, is used to solve the model on the OSeMOSYS cloud. Third, a script is used to process and create graphs for an initial analysis based on the results downloaded from the OSeMOSYS cloud.² Both the last and the first step are again to be implemented as cloud-based scripts.

Model development process

In this section, the ongoing model development process is presented, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Key project activities relating to CORE-WESM

Project phase	Activity	Timeline	Status
Conceptual WESM-County model framework (as presented in this report) (Output 1)	Develop a conceptual understanding of the National-County framework, building in experience from UK multi-scale modelling	January – June 2024	Complete
	Gather feedback on conceptual framework	June 2024	Complete
	Workflow for model development finalised	September 2024	Complete
Review of county data availability and other data sources (Output 2)	Determine essential data for the proposed framework	June 2024	Complete
	Identify data availability across three sources of data, from CEPs and via downscaling approaches	May – August 2024	Ongoing
	Develop workflow for gathering data, including collaboration with specific counties	June – August 2024	Initiated following workshop – ongoing

² This could build on work that has already been undertaken for the OSeMOSYS Global project.

	Gather data, aligning this to the work of the data repository team	July – October 2024	Ongoing
	Ensure a process for allowing counties to cross-check data estimates	October – December 2024	Not started
Build model structure, integrate data and undertake first analysis (Output 3)	Develop model structure, and integrate data	July – October 2024	Ongoing
	Undertake preliminary model runs for testing phase	October – November 2024	No tasks below started
	Model refinement process	November – December 2024	
	Final model runs	January – March 2025	
	Finalise model and documentation	March 2025	

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Annexes

A1. County Energy Plan review

Current status of CEPs development

The county energy plans (CEP) developed by each county in Kenya follow the framework provided by the INEP document (Integrated National Energy Plan). However, counties have some flexibility in selecting the different elements structuring a CEP. For instance, the methodologies to develop scenarios feeding the CEPs can be chosen by the county. Although a list of outputs is specified in the INEP framework, they vary to some extent between the different documents.

During the UK PACT phase 1, an analysis of the current status of the CEPs has been made. Out of the 47 counties, 6 counties have a complete CEP: Kitui, Marsabit, Nairobi, Nakuru, Narok, and Turkana. (Mwendwa, Leonard, and Hirmer 2023). Since then, another one, Meru has also completed its CEP.

Three main models have been used to support the development of the CEPs:

- The Energy Deliver Model (EDM), developed by IIED, which is a pro-poor approach to energy services and is the result of discussion with stakeholders selected appropriately depending on the socio-cultural context.
- The Low Emissions Analysis Platform (LEAP) is a software tool for energy policy analysis and climate change mitigation assessment developed at the Stockholm Environment Institute (Heaps 2008). It can provide an integrated and scenario-based modelling of the energy system.
- Finally, the Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) has also been developed in some counties to focus specifically on electrification pathways. OnSSET is an open-source geospatial electrification tool developed by the Energy Systems division of KTH Royal Institute of Technology (Mentis et al. 2017).

Coverage of the CEPs

The different CEPs that have been developed so far are presented in Table A1, adapted from (Millot, Mutia, and Hawkes 2023).

Table A1. CEPs summary

County	Methodology	Scenario
Kitui	EDM, Onset	Different tiers of electrification for rural households
Marsabit	Not publicly available	
Nairobi	Not publicly available	
Nakuru	LEAP	Business as usual, SDG 7, High economic growth
Narok	LEAP, OnSSET, EAE	Least cost electrification, Forced grid electrification
Turkana	Simulation model	Business as usual, Vision 2030, High GDP growth, Rapid urbanisation, Biomass policy intervention
Meru	Not publicly available	

The sectors covered by the CEP can vary slightly depending on the specificities of the county but most of them include the following elements:

- Energy resource assessment covering either only renewables (solar, wind, bioenergy, and geothermal) or also fossil fuels
- Energy consumption for the following sectors:
 - Households with very often a focus on cooking fuels and on lighting.
 - Education facilities,
 - Health facilities,
 - Enterprises/productive uses,
 - Agriculture

Data flows between the national and the county level

Data exchange needs to go both ways between the national and the county level. For instance, a minimum list of data that could be provided by the CEPs has been suggested by Ngaira et al. (2023) in the table below.

TABLE 6: Proposed 'bare minimum plus' data inputs for county energy planning

Data Point	Definition	Example of Input Information
Electricity Access Rates	What proportion of households and social institutions have access to electricity (centralised and decentralised systems)	Household Access Rates (%)
		Social Institutions (Schools and Health Care Facilities) Access Rates (%)
Access to clean cooking solutions	What proportion of households and social institutions have access to clean cooking solutions (LPG, Biomass, Electricity etc.)	Household Access Rates (%)
		Social Institutions (%)
Renewable Energy	Renewable Energy Projects within the County	Solar (# and size of projects)
		Wind (# and size of projects)
		Geothermal (# and size of projects)
Energy priorities and needs within the County	Plans to electrify specific health facilities, schools, etc.	Brief description of plan and allocated resources (KSH) <i>e.g., A Level 4 hospital in Kuresoi that is not connected to the grid that needs to be electrified. The County has allocated (X) to electrifying the hospital.</i>
		Brief description of plan and allocated resources (KSH) <i>e.g. A Community in Bahati that is 50 km from the nearest transformer and has a high population density that requires a mini-grid. The County has allocated (X) to develop a mini-grid.</i>

Some data have also been identified as being sourced from the national level and feeding into the CEPs in Leonard et al. (2023).

Table A2. Core data needs to feed into county energy planning, identified through interviews Source: (Leonard, Mwendwa, and Hirmer 2023).

Data need	Source
Grid infrastructure	KPLC – Typically willing to provide this data after bilateral approach/negotiation and instruction from MoE.
Grid connectivity	KPLC – Less willing/unable to provide this data. Sourced at present via one-off surveys instead.
Electricity access rates	KNBS – Reported to be good to work with but cannot provide this data at ward level (e.g., as needed by EDM).
Demand data by categories	KPLC – Less willing/unable to provide this data. Sourced at present via interviews, focus groups, reports, etc.
Local demographic baseline	KNBS – Reported to be good to work with but cannot provide this data at ward level (e.g., as needed by EDM).
Cross-sector development needs	National ministries and county executive committees, depending on the sector considered.

A2. CoG-UK PACT Workshop, June 2024

During June 25-27th 2024, a workshop was held in Sagana, co-hosted by the Council of Governors and UK PACT, to discuss the project and elicit feedback on the approach being taken. We ran a session titled 'Towards a county-to-national modelling framework: Combining county and national level approaches to energy system planning in support of INEP, and presented an earlier version of the approach presented in this report. Below are the key points arising from the discussions during this session.

Following the presentation of the approach, four sets of questions were considered by six different breakout groups. The following sections capture some of the key issues raised -

1. Overall concept

- *Does the modelling approach presented make sense in view of the objective of supporting the integration of county-national planning?*
- *What are the benefits and limitations of the approach proposed?*

These questions were asked to identify and understand different perspectives on the overall approach being proposed, in the context of support to the INEP process.

There seemed to be a consensus that in the main the approach was useful / makes sense, providing a more unified county-based picture at the national level. One group highlighted that it might also be an approach that could help the standardization of planning and reporting, and another that it could help bring counties together in supporting and developing county analysis, and engaging in the INEP process

It was also highlighted as a possible basis for improved resource mapping and a means to starting to build a more comprehensive county representation, including datasets. Another group raised the point that this could be an approach that provides information that counties could use to attract investment, based on information provided on investment needs and key priorities.

However, it was also evident from the discussion that there was an ongoing need to build greater understanding of the approach proposed and what it means for the counties.

Different groups highlighted potential challenges to implementing this approach –

- Lack of data. This was an emerging theme throughout the workshop, and highlights the challenge for this project. There is also the challenge of data being fragmented, and not easily available in required formats.

- Differences in CEP progress across counties. Despite the data hierarchy approach, concerns were raised about how a national picture can be built, given that some counties have yet to start their CEP.
- Lack of resources to contribute to modelling, and data collection. Again an emerging theme, this time on resource constraints at the county level to populate and work with the model.
- Lack of clarity on who the users of the model are, and limited technical expertise to engage. These are issues that the UK PACT project team needs to think through; if county stakeholders do become users, there will need to be appropriate training put in place to ensure sustainability of the tool.
- Questions were also raised as to whether such a modelling approach would be able to sufficiently differentiate between different county priorities.

Another important issue raised concerned the fact that the INEP process had not been finalised – and therefore there were questions as to the alignment with the process that eventually emerged. A further issue identified by one group was that counties are bounded by their CIDP and therefore there could be challenges with alignment with the proposed modelling approach.

2. Model design

- *Are the correct features of counties being adequately represented in the WESM framework, in view of representing the CEPs?*

This question was posed to get feedback on the model design so that it can be further refined to support both county and national planners. The figure below, and Table 2 in the report were used as information to help facilitate discussion.

In general, feedback was that this was the correct focus – but that considerations could be given to the following –

- Waste management, given the role that this sector could play as a source of energy
- Transport, as a sector that fell under county jurisdiction and required consideration in CEPs
- Cooling was also flagged as a demand for energy, notably in the future, and for which interventions might be needed to address consumption levels (incl. building design)
- Mining was also mentioned as a potentially important activity to capture at the county scale
- On renewable resources, some groups thought it was important to ensure a comprehensive representation across all types of renewables.
- There was also the questions of whether it might be useful to capture imports in those counties bordering other countries.

A couple of breakout groups / stakeholders questioned the need for representation of decentralised generation at the county level as this was not a devolved function.

3. Data availability

- *Does the data hierarchy make sense in how we identify data sources?*
- *Can you provide information on data sources, in view of the model design?*
- *Would any counties be interested in working more closely with the modelling team on data sourcing, to help shape ongoing data workflow for this modelling?*

This set of questions were considered to better understand data availability and gaps, and how these might be addressed; and which counties might be interested in working more closely with the UK PACT team on data needs.

In general, the feedback highlighted that the data hierarchy approach made sense. There was also a willingness across many of the counties to get involved in supporting the process of identifying data. Some groups considered it important to incorporate as much county level data as was feasible to do so – to ensure representation of county specifics. This might include surveys undertaken, data used to support CIDPs, and other county level statistics across departments.

Some counties that have not yet started the CEP process were keen to be involved in the process, in terms of gaining support for data collection and modelling. However, it was reiterated by a number of stakeholders that both capacity building and budgets would be needed to bring some counties up to the level of others, given some have made limited progress on the CEP process to date.

Some counties highlighted that they had been quite active in the collection of data e.g. Nakuru, Turkana, with Turkana having developed a database to hold different datasets. However, there were also issues raised around data access, with some data not necessarily available (given restrictions) or in the right format for sharing. Data management and processing for use by other users is not always in place.

Other national data providers potentially holding useful data that UK PACT could coordinate with include KNBS, EPRA, KPLC and REREC.

Finally, an important challenge was put forward around how indigenous knowledge might be incorporated in the process alongside more formal statistics.

4. User group and capacity

- *Who should be involved in developing, using and maintaining the model in the future?*
- *Does it make sense to embed this approach in an institution (ministry, university) and / or could it be curated by the CCG Special Interest Group (SIG) on energy planning?*
- *Are there any further reflections on accessibility or usability of the model?*

This discussion topic was considered to identify who might be the user group for this model, and consider capacity building needs.

Some counties stated the importance for county energy directorates to be strongly involved in the development and use of the model. However, it was also stressed that capacity building would be an important requisite for county involvement to allow for effective partnership.

County stakeholders also highlighted the need for coordination between counties and national government and CoG in the development and use of the model. One group highlighted the relevance of the energy planning SIGs in this regard.

Some stakeholders also highlighted the importance of including academic partners to try and build capacity – and to help embed the modelling approach.